

BIODIVERSITY IN FOCUS: KEY INSIGHTS AND OUTCOMES FROM CBD COP16

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INTRODUCTION

Greetings, my name is Yunjoo Cho, and I am currently a Master's student at the University of Michigan School of Environment and Sustainability, specializing in Environmental Policy and Sustainable Systems. I had the opportunity to attend the Sixteenth Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (COP16) in Cali, Colombia, from October 21 to 28, 2024. I joined as an official Youth delegate for the Global Youth Biodiversity Network USA Chapter, through which I received official accreditation.

During my eight days at COP16, I attended over 30 side events and observed two negotiation sessions. This report is based on notes I personally took during presentations and panel discussions at the events I attended. I tried to add the information of the speakers as much as I could, but not all of the speakers are introduced here. For the introductory section, I introduced key takeaways from COP16 referring to an article of Carbon Brief and the official Convention on Biological Diversity website.

Please note that this report does not cover every side event at COP16; rather, it includes content from those events I found particularly engaging. Additionally, the perspectives and statements presented here belong solely to the speakers at each event; my own opinions are not included in this report.

KEY NEGOTIATION TAKEAWAYS

The Sixteenth Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity (COP16) took place from October 21 to November 2 in Cali, Colombia. COP16 was the first COP since countries adopted the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF) in 2022 to halt biodiversity loss by 2030. Countries were tasked with submitting their National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs), new national biodiversity pledges that align with the KMGBF goals, by October 21, the opening day of COP16. However, only 26 out of 196 countries met the deadline, and by November 2, the closing day of COP16, a total of 44 countries had submitted their NBSAPs. Biodiversity-rich countries such as Brazil and Colombia claimed that they missed the deadline because it took a long time to engage various stakeholders to conserve their numerous biodiversity sites, while most developing countries claimed that they missed the deadline because organizations such as the Global Environment Facility failed to deliver biodiversity funding in time. Countries that failed to submit their NBSAPs by the opening day of COP16 were asked to submit national targets, and 119 countries submitted national biodiversity targets. For reference, the United States is one of the 17 megadiverse (biodiversity-rich) countries, but is not a party to the CBD.

Countries with new biodiversity pledges (NBSAPs)

Image source: Carbon Brief

Digital Sequence Information

Digital Sequence Information (DSI) refers to genetic data derived from plants and animals. This genetic information is often collected in biodiversity-rich developing countries, then used by companies mainly headquartered in wealthier nations to develop products like medicines, cosmetics, and foods. For this reason, developing countries and Indigenous communities have long called for an international system that ensures the benefits from DSI are fairly shared with the regions and communities from which these resources originate. While an initial framework for benefit-sharing was introduced at COP15 in Montreal, significant gaps remained in the details, preventing full implementation.

At COP16, countries reached a landmark agreement to create a global fund called the "Cali Fund," supported by a multilateral structure for fair benefit-sharing. Under this agreement, companies in sectors like pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, agriculture, nutraceuticals, and technology are expected to contribute to the fund, donating either 1% of their profits or 0.1% of their revenue. More than half of the fund's resources will be dedicated to addressing the self-identified needs of Indigenous peoples and local communities, focusing on supporting women and youth. This support may be distributed through government channels or directly to institutions chosen by the communities themselves, with some funds also allocated to capacity-building and technology transfer.

Indigenous People and Local Communities & Article 8(j)

The Parties adopted a new Program of Work to enhance the role of indigenous peoples and local communities in achieving the Convention's goals of conserving biodiversity, using it sustainably, and sharing benefits fairly. This program supports the implementation of the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF) and emphasizes the importance of indigenous knowledge and contributions on a global level.

A permanent subsidiary body dedicated to Article 8(j) and related provisions will also be established, with its structure being developed by 2026. This body aims to increase the involvement and representation of indigenous peoples and local communities in the Convention.

Additionally, the Parties recognized the significant role of people of African descent who maintain traditional ways of life in promoting biodiversity conservation and sustainable use.

Biodiversity Finance (negotiation postponed to 2025)

In Montreal, countries established an interim fund called the Global Biodiversity Framework Fund (GBFF) under the Global Environment Facility (GEF). So far, seven developed countries have contributed around \$250 million, with additional funding discussions planned in 2025 to create a “Strategy for Resource Mobilization.” This strategy aims to secure \$200 billion annually by 2030 to support global biodiversity efforts and to redirect \$500 billion each year away from harmful subsidies by the same date, both of which are goals of the Kunming–Montréal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF).

The GBFF, created at COP15 and operational within a year, accepts donations from governments, private sectors, and philanthropies. It funds impactful biodiversity projects in developing regions, prioritizing vulnerable areas such as small island states and transitional economies. To date, 11 countries and the Government of Quebec have pledged nearly \$400 million to the GBFF, including \$163 million announced during COP16.

Additionally, at COP16, the Kunming Biodiversity Fund (KBF) was launched with a \$200 million contribution from China. The KBF will support accelerated efforts toward the 2030 Agenda, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and the long-term 2050 goals of the KMGBF, focusing on developing countries.

Biodiversity and Health (voluntary)

Countries approved a new Global Action Plan on Biodiversity and Health. This voluntary plan emphasizes the connection between biodiversity and human health and aims to help governments and stakeholders incorporate these links into their policies and programs.

The plan highlights the importance of educating people about how biodiversity impacts health and calls for stronger policies to support sustainable ecosystems, traditional medicine, and habitat protection. It also focuses on protecting vulnerable groups, such as Indigenous peoples, who rely on local biodiversity for food, medicine, and cultural practices, as well as on engaging youth, who are seen as essential to conservation and health efforts. It also aims to bring together health experts, conservationists, and policymakers to work on these shared goals.

Further Steps

The COP16 has been postponed to 2025, with no agreement yet reached on biodiversity financing. It is expected to take place alongside the intersessional talks planned for next year, but no exact schedules are fixed yet. Meanwhile, COP17 has been scheduled to occur in Yerevan, Armenia in 2026.

IPBES

Intergovernmental Science–Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

SESSION 1. IPBES Science X Policy

Q1. How can IPBES and IPCC inform policy action?

In response to this question, a representative from the Democratic Republic of the Congo highlighted a significant coordination gap between IPBES (Intergovernmental Science–Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services) and IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change). They noted that integrating National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plans (NBSAPs) with Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs) could provide valuable opportunities for collaboration between the two organizations. While both IPBES and IPCC are highly relevant for informing policy, the challenge lies in translating their findings into actionable national-level policies that bridge the gap between biodiversity and climate goals.

Another participant from Morocco acknowledged that IPBES and IPCC often diverge in their decisions, partly due to varying political contexts. Scientific communities involved in both climate change and biodiversity initiatives could play a critical role in helping to harmonize the efforts of these two organizations.

A representative from Colombia emphasized that while IPBES assessments are useful for policy guidance, they are not yet fully leveraged at the national and subnational levels. Focal points for both IPBES and IPCC do exist and cooperate, but there is potential for deeper integration. Making IPBES assessments relevant for local governments is essential for translating global findings into practical action, and governments must improve the dissemination of these insights.

A representative from the European Commission underscored the importance of science in addressing climate and biodiversity challenges. He referenced the transformative message of IPBES's 2019 report, which called for a fundamental shift in how we perceive nature and biodiversity. To make progress, he highlighted the need for changes within the scientific system, including the incorporation of Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK). Additionally, they suggested that the COP (Conference of the Parties) structure and negotiation processes require reorganization, as the current aggregated format consumes excessive time.

Ms. Ana Maria from IPBES urged participants to consult the joint IPBES-IPCC report, which exemplifies science working collaboratively while policy efforts remain somewhat compartmentalized. She advocated for incorporating social and economic data to create a comprehensive framework that bridges the gap between policymaking and societal needs.

Key Takeaways for Strengthening IPBES-IPCC Cooperation

Several themes emerged as critical to enhancing the IPBES and IPCC's contribution to policy action. Firstly, there is a strong need to engage in open dialogue around international standards and practices that can guide cooperative approaches. Establishing broader paradigms for engaging IPBES within the science-policy dialogue will be essential. The goal should be to bring together individuals and institutions willing to tackle these challenges collaboratively, setting the stage for a more integrated, actionable approach to climate and biodiversity policy.

Q2. How can knowledge on biodiversity and climate change be more relevant for decision-making?

This question focused on making biodiversity and climate change data more applicable for policymakers. Participants stressed the importance of aligning scientific assessments with local governance frameworks to ensure that the data produced is relevant and useful for on-the-ground decision-making. Effective dissemination and localization of IPBES and IPCC findings could greatly enhance the decision-making processes at various governmental levels.

Q3. Where can scientific inputs help to implement the Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF)?

To support the implementation of the Global Biodiversity Framework, participants agreed that there must be a more cohesive approach to scientific input, particularly by integrating biodiversity and climate considerations within a unified framework. This approach would not only aid in the adoption of GBF goals but also ensure that the progress made is measurable, actionable, and scalable across different regions and policy contexts.

SESSION 2. Sustainable Use, Values and Invasive Alien Species Assessments from IPBES

Overview of the IPBES Assessment Process

The Intergovernmental Science–Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) assessment process combines scientific literature with Indigenous and Local Community (IPLCs) knowledge to evaluate pressing biodiversity and ecosystem challenges. These assessments explore the causes of biodiversity loss, potential solutions, and the socio-cultural dimensions of conservation, informing global biodiversity policy. Key completed assessments are detailed below, highlighting significant findings, methodologies, and implications.

Diverse Values and Valuation of Nature Assessment

Led by Professor Mike Christie, a professor of Environmental and Ecological Economics of Aberystwyth University, this assessment examines how biodiversity loss is influenced by the ways nature is valued, often in market-based terms within political and economic frameworks. Findings indicate that addressing the biodiversity crisis requires acknowledging a diverse array of values beyond economic metrics, suggesting that policy should encompass a wider typology of values that captures people's relationships with nature, including social norms and policies. The assessment identifies over fifty methods from various

disciplines and knowledge systems for valuing nature, underscoring the need for institutions that support the integration of different values in decision-making processes. It argues that transformative change depends on moving beyond short-term, individual material gains to embrace values aligned with sustainability. This shift can be driven by targeting specific points of influence rooted in diverse values. Respecting Indigenous and Local Knowledge (ILK) and its associated values is essential for ensuring equitable outcomes that honor varied ways of life.

Incorporating Diverse Values of Biodiversity into COP16 Agenda

Agenda item 18 at COP16 focuses on integrating the key findings from the Values Assessment (VA) into the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) framework. Section C of the Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) highlights the VA's contributions, especially for Indigenous and Local Community values. Goal B aims to ensure that nature's contributions are valued for future generations by 2050, while Goal C focuses on equity and justice in the benefit-sharing of genetic resources. Target 14 of the GBF promotes the integration of biodiversity and diverse values into policies, regulations, poverty eradication strategies, environmental assessments, and Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs).

Sustainable Use of Wild Species Assessment

The IPBES Sustainable Use of Wild Species assessment examines case studies worldwide, drawing on multiple knowledge systems, including ILK. The report emphasizes the importance of strong governance systems, such as customary law, in developing solutions like monitoring and adaptive management, which are essential for the sustainable management of wild species. Wild species play a significant role in food security, and this assessment frames their use in terms of five main practices and eight uses. Previously under-recognized drivers affecting wild species are also explored, including the upstream impacts on population health, consumer preferences related to health benefits, and the influence of online trade and social media on demand.

Invasive Alien Species (IAS) Assessment

Led by Professor Anibal Pauchard from the University of Concepción, this assessment focuses on alien species, which are plants, animals, and other organisms introduced through human activity. Biological invasions, whether intentional or accidental, have led to the establishment of over 37,000 alien species globally, with 2,500 identified as invasive and harmful to ecosystems and people. IAS contribute to species extinction, impose economic costs, and reduce quality of life. In 2019, the global cost of biological invasions exceeded \$423 billion, with 80% of their impacts on nature's contributions to people deemed negative. Current policies are inadequate, as 83% of countries lack legislation specifically targeting IAS prevention and control.

Management and Prevention Strategies for Invasive Alien Species

The assessment outlines effective management strategies for IAS, emphasizing that prevention is the most effective approach. Key strategies include managing introduction pathways to stop IAS spread, with strict import controls being critical in marine and interconnected water systems. Where IAS are established, local or landscape-scale interventions are recommended, such as site-based or ecosystem-based approaches. Eradication, containment, and control efforts are crucial in terrestrial and closed water systems, alongside adaptive management to restore ecosystem functions. Integrated governance is essential, requiring national strategies, policy alignment, IPLCs engagement, financing, and data sharing. Target 6 of the GBF reinforces the need for these comprehensive and coordinated responses to effectively address IAS challenges.

SESSION 3. IPBES Ongoing Assessments

Overview of the IPBES Second Global Assessment

The IPBES Second Global Assessment is designed to build upon the findings of the first assessment while maintaining a broad scope. It will comprehensively cover terrestrial and inland water ecosystems, with a significant emphasis on marine ecosystems. The assessment aims to review new evidence on the status and trends of biodiversity, the causative factors related to multiple drivers, and the consequences for both people and nature.

Highlighting Positive Examples and Addressing Critical Gaps

This assessment will showcase positive examples that demonstrate enabling conditions for success and indicate ways in which these approaches can be extended or replicated on various scales to contribute to global efforts. Additionally, it will address critical gaps identified in the first Global Assessment, particularly the need for increased focus on oceans and seas, differentiation within and among regions, and the distribution of nature's contributions to people across different societal groups, including considerations of gender. The assessment will also examine potential tipping points and interactions among multiple drivers, as well as urban challenges.

Exploring Scenarios and Identifying Actors

The Second Global Assessment will highlight new evidence regarding various scenarios and outline critical pathways for achieving global societal goals. It will identify the roles of various stakeholders, including governments, Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs), the private sector, and civil society, in delivering the essential building blocks for transformative change. A dedicated chapter will focus specifically on Indigenous Local Knowledge (ILK).

Useful Tools for Biodiversity Assessment

Several useful tools will aid in the assessment process, including the Global Biodiversity Information Facilitator (GBIF), Ocean Best Practices, and the Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS).

Ongoing IPBES Assessments

The IPBES is currently conducting several ongoing assessments, including those focusing on Business and Biodiversity, Transformative Change, and the interlinkages among biodiversity, water, food, and health, referred to as the Nexus Assessment.

1) Business and Biodiversity Assessment

This assessment comprises several key sections: a Summary for Policymakers (SPM), an exploration of how business depends on and impacts biodiversity, approaches for measuring business dependencies and impacts, options for action by businesses, and recommendations for creating an enabling environment for business through government and civil society actions. The assessment is highly relevant to the Convention on Biological Diversity, addressing the relationship between businesses and biodiversity, and exploring how businesses can contribute to achieving the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF).

2) Transformative Change Assessment

The scope of the Transformative Change assessment, co-authored by Professor Arun Agrawal from the University of Michigan, includes an evaluation of different visions, scenarios, and pathways for a sustainable world, aligning with the 2050 vision for biodiversity and considering the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including perspectives from IPLCs. This report will examine the determinants of transformative change, obstacles faced, and practical options for fostering, accelerating, and maintaining such change. It will also provide concrete steps necessary for achieving sustainable outcomes, integrating science and ILK with diverse ethical perspectives.

3) Thematic Assessment of the Nexus Among Biodiversity, Water, Food, and Health

The Nexus Assessment will evaluate the scale of knowledge regarding past, present, and future trends in the interlinkages among biodiversity, water, food, and health. It will highlight key thresholds, feedback, and resilience in these linkages, as well as opportunities and trade-offs among various response options. This assessment will include strategies for delivering sustainable biodiversity-related approaches to climate change adaptation and mitigation, focusing on global, regional, and subregional similarities and differences.

The assessment will explore policy and sociopolitical options across the nexus, addressing governance issues, scaling response options, and identifying decision-support tools. It will evaluate multisectoral approaches that build on synergies between the nexus sectors, considering institutions, collective action, enablers and barriers, and regional differences. Additionally, the assessment will analyze financial flows related to biodiversity and the nexus, assessing funding gaps and potential future scenarios.

This thematic assessment will also underscore the relationship between biodiversity and health, promoting measures to enhance health outcomes, and will address biodiversity's intersection with climate change, focusing on policies that conserve and restore biodiversity while meeting global objectives. Furthermore, it will examine the diverse values of biodiversity, including the roles of ILK and different perceptions of quality of life, emphasizing the intrinsic values of nature and mechanisms that reflect Indigenous worldviews.

BUSINESS AND BIODIVERSITY

SESSION 1. High-Level Principles of Biodiversity Credit Alliance

Ms. Midori Paxton from the UNDP Nature Hub discussed the global finance gap for biodiversity, currently estimated at around \$700 billion per year. She emphasized the need to unlock public finance and noted that biodiversity credits are emerging as a potential funding mechanism for the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Biodiversity credits were designed with integrity and inclusivity in mind to benefit a wide range of stakeholders, including Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs). UNDP is working to coordinate various networks and workstreams, such as social and environmental safeguards and voluntary carbon markets. Additionally, UNDP manages the GEF Small Grant Program and BIOFIN, which is focusing on the digitalization of climate financing. In January 2025, UNDP plans to launch high-level principles that will provide an assessment framework and align with advisory panels from the Biodiversity Credit Alliance.

Mr. Alessandro Valentini from the World Economic Forum provided insights into the progress of the biodiversity credit framework. The first working group focused on establishing an integrity framework for biodiversity credits, emphasizing the importance of defining and respecting these standards. During COP15, the initial principles were published, followed by a consultation phase. He emphasized the need to incorporate equity into the framework to ensure that biodiversity credits are guided by fair and transparent principles that the market respects.

Mr. Sören Müller from the Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development addressed the role of domestic and private finance in biodiversity, highlighting the private sector's interest in funding conservation. A draft of the high-level principles by the Biodiversity Credit Alliance has been released, though there are varying opinions about biodiversity credits. Despite the differences, he argued that biodiversity credits are essential for building a cohesive global biodiversity framework. He stressed the importance of creating value through biodiversity credits and suggested that the Biodiversity Credit Alliance should be monitored more efficiently as it develops.

Panel Discussion

In a panel discussion moderated by Ms. Samantha Lacey from The Biodiversity Consultancy, several stakeholders shared their perspectives on biodiversity credits.

A representative from the Regional Bank of Far South raised concerns about "greenhushing" in the use of biodiversity credits, noting that the Scottish government is currently testing the trustworthiness of this approach. Mr. Owain Griffiths from Volvo Cars discussed the benefits of biodiversity credits, specifically in understanding the costs associated with credits and how these can justify the biodiversity footprint of products. He emphasized that biodiversity credits differ from carbon credits and noted the need for reporting biodiversity impacts under frameworks like CSRD and Green Claims.

A representative from the Bank of Brazil shared that Latin America and the Caribbean are still behind in adopting biodiversity and carbon credits. She also emphasized the importance of recognizing the rights of nature and IPLCs in biodiversity credits. Market governance, she argued, is critical, which is why UNDP is beginning to engage with IPLCs to integrate Indigenous Local Knowledge (ILK) into the biodiversity credit system.

Mr. Juan Camilo Pinto from the Ministry of Environment in Colombia highlighted the need to build trust in biodiversity credits, noting that these credits differ fundamentally from carbon credits. The value of biodiversity credits is tied to ecosystem services, which are complex and require clear high-level principles to guide government decisions.

Ms. Hanieh Moghani, representing IPLCs from the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, shared that there are significant barriers to implementing biodiversity credits in the MENA region. While there are existing practices, their benefits are not widely apparent. She called for a stronger human rights approach to improve biodiversity credit systems and pointed out successful policy examples in countries like Indonesia, Namibia, and Ghana.

SESSION 2. Biodiversity Credit Metrics

Session Overview: Standardizing Biodiversity Credits

Moderator Dr. Richard Field from the University of Nottingham led a session featuring speakers from SeaTrees, ERA Brazil, Biodiversity Credit Alliance, and Toha Network. The session explored the complex balance between the standardization and flexibility of biodiversity credits, emphasizing the need for metrics that can both support consistent market comparisons and accommodate diverse ecological contexts.

Standardization vs. Flexibility in Biodiversity Credits

Mr. Orion McCarthy from SeaTrees highlighted the benefits and challenges of standardized biodiversity credit metrics. Standardized metrics can facilitate project comparisons across regions, but flexibility is essential to account for local ecological factors. A core question is how to select appropriate metrics that accurately reflect ecosystem conditions and project impacts. The table is shown next page about the criteria necessary to consider when selecting appropriate metrics for biodiversity credits.

Step	Screening Criteria	Screening Question
1. Come up with a shortlist of possible metrics	Ecologically-relevant	Does the metric have a well-understood relationship with biodiversity (via traditional knowledge or scientific literature)?
	Responsive	Is the metric responsive and sensitive to restoration over relevant timescales?
	Variable	Does the metric show natural variability between high-and low-biodiversity sites?
	Directional	Can change over time be clearly interpreted as favorable or unfavorable?
	Simple	Is the metric easy to understand?
2. Select metrics that fit local context	Goal-oriented	Is the metric relevant to specific restoration goals?
	Locally-relevant	Is the metric regionally appropriate?
	Measurable	Are local collaborators able to measure the metric accurately in a cost- and time- effective manner?
	Synergistic	Is the metric already measured by existing monitoring programs or nearby restoration projects?
3. Ensure overall suite of metrics is appropriate	Comprehensive	Does the basket-of-metrics encompass all relevant aspects of biodiversity?
	Non-redundant	Does the basket-of-metrics avoid duplicate metrics of the same ecosystem process?

ERA Brazil's Biodiversity Credits Protocol

Ms. Hannah Simmons from ERA Brazil presented ERA's biodiversity credit protocol, which focuses on inclusivity, transparency, and accessibility. Key principles include the active involvement of Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs), and a commitment to low costs and barriers to entry. Unlike biodiversity offsetting, ERA's credits aim to generate positive contributions to nature rather than compensating for environmental degradation. The crediting framework bases the number of credits on habitat area multiplied by stewardship factors, emphasizing transparency in setting prices, which are based on conservation costs. Credits are retired upon purchase, avoiding secondary market trading. ERA Brazil's credit protocol includes a structured approach to metrics: one credit represents stewardship over one hectare of habitat for one year, targeting umbrella species as indicators of ecosystem health. Metrics are broken down into four primary components: health of umbrella species (tracked through presence, distribution, and monitoring), habitat quality (evaluated using indexes like the Shannon Diversity Index), local interventions tailored to specific threats (such as fire prevention and community engagement), and habitat area. These components together ensure that the credits reflect both broad and context-specific biodiversity factors.

Credibility and Comparability in Biodiversity Credits

Mr. Josh Brann from the Biodiversity Credit Alliance discussed findings from surveys examining factors for establishing credibility in biodiversity credits. Respondents emphasized the importance of transparent technology and metrics grounded in scientific validation. Popular metrics and measurement tools cited include the GRI Biodiversity Standard, TNFD Core Global Metrics, and the Biodiversity NetGain Calculator. Survey participants expressed a preference for comparable units of measurement tailored to similar ecosystems rather than a single standardized unit.

The Biodiversity Credit Alliance identified key questions for advancing the credibility of biodiversity credits. These include distinguishing attributes among biodiversity credits, assessing which attributes are critical for the market context, and determining how to meet buyer needs when they make claims based on biodiversity credit purchases. Developing a framework or tool to describe

biodiversity credits in a standardized way would enhance comparability, especially given the 50+ existing biodiversity credit methodologies, each with unique metrics and geographic applications.

Proposed 24 Key Attributes for Comparability

1. Credit name	2. Project name	3. Originating seller	4. 3rd party certification/verification
5. Issuance date	6. Price	7. Any linked credits	8. Credit generation methodology
9. MRV authority	10. Insurance or risk mitigation	11. Typology	12. Unit description
13. Biodiversity/nature target	14. Biodiversity indicator/metric applied	15. Credit unit sale	16. Credit unit geographic designation
17. Geographic location	18. Project scale	19. Project scale type	20. Credit duration/permanence duration
21. Nature of IPLC engagement	22. Local socio-economic benefits	23. Identified co-benefits	24. Associated claim statement

Challenges of Standardizing Biodiversity Credits

Standardizing a single unit for biodiversity credits is complex, given the variability in data sharing practices and project contexts. Although linking biodiversity credits to established carbon credits could attract corporate interest, achieving a unified market demand remains challenging. Efforts are underway to develop a standardized communication approach for biodiversity credits, emphasizing transparency and comparability without compromising the diversity of methodologies essential for addressing ecosystems and biodiversity goals.

SESSION 3. How to Report on Biodiversity and Meet Target 15 of the KMGBF

Understanding Biodiversity in SMEs

Ms. Isabelle Combarel from Arkea Capital emphasized that small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) often lack a thorough understanding of biodiversity. To address this gap, there is a pressing need for training and the use of case studies to educate SME leaders, particularly CEOs. She highlighted the necessity of changing investment strategies to prioritize biodiversity.

Funding Nature-based Solutions

Mr. Martin Powell of AXA Group, an insurance company, noted that current funding levels for Nature-based Solutions (NbS) and regenerative agriculture are insufficient. He posed the question of how to achieve better funding. He argued for precise evaluation of losses associated with environmental issues such as air and water pollution, which ultimately serve to protect nature. He stated that integrating nature into investment and impact assessments is a key question. He mentioned ongoing projects, including a collaboration with Ocean Alliance to develop a coastal risk index, which aims to quantify economic losses. He cited specific examples, such as the Mesoamerica Coral Reef project, where efforts are being made to remove silt to revitalize coral reefs that support the livelihoods of 12,000 fishermen. Additionally, he discussed the impact of extreme heatwaves on workers in Hong Kong.

Advice for Implementing Target 15

When asked for advice on implementing Target 15, Mr. Powell suggested that companies measure their materiality concerning nature and maintain transparency in their operations. Mr. Nicolas Boquet from AFEP recommended providing opportunities for scientific input and governance. Ms. Combarel reiterated the importance of collaborative finance, while Mr. Harold Pauwels from the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) stressed the necessity for SMEs to grasp the importance of biodiversity, suggesting that tools such as water filters and ENCORE should be accessible and accompanied by educational initiatives. Ms. Stephanie Paquin Jaloux from Schneider Electric advocated for starting with small initiatives.

Challenges in Sustainable Supply Chains

In response to a question from a global conglomerate in the steel industry regarding the lack of market support and its impact on downstream suppliers, Ms. Stephanie Paquin Jaloux from the Schneider Electric highlighted its commitment to broadening the use of sustainable materials. The company collaborates with steelmakers to drive innovation toward less energy-intensive processes and underscored the importance of transparency and dialogue in these efforts. The Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) focuses on value chains, which will require suppliers to explain their sustainability efforts.

Motivating Compliance in SMEs

Another inquiry centered on the challenge of standardizing frameworks and motivating SMEs and entrepreneurs for compliance, suggesting the need for a bottom-up approach supported by public systems. Ms. Combarel suggested that the term "ESG" can be used to incentivize CEOs regarding financing. She advocated for internal training by investing in personnel from within the company to foster compliance. She added there are free tools for entrepreneurs, recommending resources like the WWF Risk Filter.

Navigating Multiple Frameworks

When addressing the challenge of managing various frameworks, the Mr. Pauwels stated that the focus should be on materiality, which relates to impact. They acknowledged the existing pushback against nature assessments, emphasizing the need for transparency and accountability.

Cost of Reporting and Framework Simplification

A final question addressed the high costs of reporting and the proliferation of different frameworks, which can lead to substantial financial waste. The importance of the CSRD was reiterated as a means of enhancing transparency. Mr. Pauwels highlighted that while reporting methodologies and tools are essential, each sector has unique needs that must be considered. They cautioned that oversimplifying frameworks could result in a loss of diversity in approaches to sustainability.

FINANCE AND BIODIVERSITY

SESSION 1. Building Policy for Nature Finance

Mobilizing Private Finance for Biodiversity Targets: Policy and Regulatory Approaches

Addressing Information Gaps in Nature-Related Risk Assessments

One significant barrier to mobilizing private finance for biodiversity lies in the information gap between governments and private companies, particularly concerning biodiversity hotspots. As businesses and financial institutions begin conducting risk assessments related to nature loss, they often lack specific data about critical biodiversity areas. Bridging this information gap requires enhanced transparency and communication between governments and stakeholders to ensure that private finance aligns with biodiversity goals. Without such data, private companies may overlook or undervalue biodiversity risks, limiting their engagement in conservation-focused investments.

Strengthening the Role of Financial Regulators and Jurisdictional Support

Financial regulators have an important role in encouraging the financial sector to prioritize nature-related issues. At the micro-level, central banks can implement frameworks that support biodiversity through risk disclosures and other nature-related reporting requirements. On a broader scale, regulatory support at the jurisdictional level can aid NBSAPs, ensuring financial policies are aligned with national biodiversity targets. Central banks, such as the Brazilian Central Bank, are already setting a precedent by introducing monetary financial disclosures aimed at building capacity for biodiversity finance within private banks. This approach points to nature-related financial disclosures as a future regulatory step to reinforce the private sector's engagement with biodiversity goals.

Limitations of Voluntary Disclosures and the Need for Mandates

While voluntary nature-related disclosures have gained some traction, they often fall short of driving meaningful change. Voluntary efforts lack the enforceability needed to ensure widespread adoption, leading to inconsistent engagement and insufficient investment in biodiversity targets. For the financial sector to genuinely contribute to biodiversity conservation, regulatory bodies must consider mandatory disclosure requirements that emphasize biodiversity risks alongside traditional financial risks. Such mandates would provide clear expectations for private companies and financial institutions, creating a more uniform approach to biodiversity finance.

Biodiversity Finance as a Foundation for Private Sector Engagement

Biodiversity finance is an emerging area that provides an entry point for private sector involvement in biodiversity targets. Financial supervisors and regulatory bodies can build confidence in this sector by signaling a shift toward nature-based finance as a priority. By encouraging biodiversity finance as a mainstream investment category, policymakers can create an environment where private investors see biodiversity projects as viable and profitable. This message is essential for guiding the private sector towards active participation in NBSAP implementation.

Building on Climate Finance Foundations

In countries like Mexico, where regulators have engaged with climate change issues for over a decade, there is now an opportunity to extend this dialogue to include biodiversity and nature finance. The established framework for climate finance provides a foundation on which discussions about biodiversity finance can build. As private sector actors and regulators are already familiar with climate-related policies, introducing biodiversity finance as an extension of these concepts can encourage a smoother transition and greater acceptance.

Public-Private Partnerships for Biodiversity Conservation

Public-private partnerships (PPPs) offer a practical model for advancing biodiversity finance. By involving the private sector in public conservation initiatives, such as forest restoration projects, PPPs can demonstrate that nature restoration aligns with profitability. This approach has started to gain recognition, showing the private sector that investing in biodiversity is not only socially responsible but can also be financially rewarding. A PPP model tailored to biodiversity conservation can create pathways for private finance to directly support NBSAP goals while showcasing the profitability of nature-positive investments.

SESSION 2. Scaling and De-risking Strategies and Incentives for Private Investment in NBSAP

Strategies for De-Risking Biodiversity Investments under GBF Target 19

Key Programs and Strategies for De-Risking

1. Mesoamerica Reef Fund: This initiative focuses on mobilizing funds for reef-positive businesses across Mesoamerica, particularly in Latin American and Caribbean (LAC) regions where such funding remains underdeveloped.

2. BIOFIN by UNDP: BIOFIN operates with three main objectives: (1) establishing an environment conducive to nature-positive financing, (2) creating sustainable and innovative financing solutions for nature-positive activities, and (3) enhancing capacity, raising awareness, and developing knowledge products. The program seeks to transform business opportunities to align with nature-positive goals and convert aspirations into tangible, finance-driven actions.

3. Natura Cosmetics, Brazil: Natura collaborates with Amazon communities, implementing a blended finance approach through partnerships with organizations such as VERT. These partnerships aim to enhance funding for biodiversity initiatives in the Amazon.

Examples of Concessional Finance, Loans, and Guarantees for Nature-Positive Outcomes

1. Natura and IFC Partnership: Information on the outcomes of this project is available on the International Finance Corporation (IFC) website, showcasing the project's results for tropical investors. A pilot project has been completed, and the first investment cycle is anticipated.
2. Mesoamerica Reef Fund: To attract more funding, the fund explores creative methods of de-risking investments, including the potential of insurance as a tool to mitigate financial risks for reef conservation projects.

Contribution of Blended Finance to NBSAP Implementation

1. BIOFIN Zambia: The Biodiversity Expenditure Review in Zambia examines the biodiversity finance landscape. While public funding is sufficient to meet NBSAP goals, private sector participation remains low. To address this gap, the BIOFIN program promotes green bond markets, enabling companies to pursue nature-positive finance. By lobbying for incentives, BIOFIN Zambia successfully secured private sector financing, including investments from an energy company. A Green Finance Strategy, in partnership with the government, further assesses and scales the effectiveness of green bonds and loans in supporting NBSAP goals.
2. Mesoamerica Reef Fund and CCAD Framework: Following the framework of the Central American Commission for Environment and Development (CCAD), the Mesoamerica Reef Fund has seen growth in private sector involvement for conservation financing.
3. Role of Governments and MDBs in De-Risking: Government and Multilateral Development Bank (MDB) involvement is critical in de-risking investments to attract contributions from various sectors. The Mesoamerica Reef Fund receives support from the Global Environment Facility (GEF) and seeks opportunities to foster community engagement with government initiatives.

Barriers to Developing New Incentives

1. BIOFIN Challenges: Physical incentives for nature-positive financing are difficult to establish. Aligning expectations between government requests and achievable outcomes presents a challenge. In Zambia, frequent natural disasters underscore the need to shift policymakers' perspectives by empirically highlighting the risks of excluding nature-positive considerations in finance.

2. Finance Knowledge Gaps: Conservationists often have strong project concepts but lack financial expertise. To address political and financial barriers, the next cohort of programs will focus on raising awareness of reef importance and mobilizing private funding for biodiversity conservation.

Approach to Development Finance

1. Community Involvement and Low-Cost Interventions: Although the costs of certain initiatives are relatively low, collaborative efforts are needed to ensure community involvement in biodiversity finance.

2. Africa's Experience with MDBs and Blended Finance: In African regions, MDBs and blended finance mechanisms are employed to de-risk nature-positive investments, which in turn creates further opportunities for MDBs to support conservation activities.

SESSION 3. World Biodiversity Summit

The Road to \$200 Billion: Finance Strategies for Biodiversity Action

Biodiversity Finance: Essential Insights and Strategies

Overview of Funding Needs and Short-Term Roadmap

Ms. Noor Yafai, European Director of The Nature Conservancy (TNC), emphasized that an estimated \$700 billion per year is necessary to restore global biodiversity. Public funding is crucial for this goal, and in the short term, establishing a roadmap for mobilizing \$25 billion is essential. Donors should work toward mainstreaming biodiversity funding in their portfolios. Public banks and multilateral development banks (MDBs) are beginning to incorporate biodiversity considerations into their frameworks. Addressing harmful subsidies and developing thoughtful policies for biodiversity credit allocation are key steps for effective funding. TNC will soon launch a new nature finance dashboard and a biodiversity credit initiative, with a focus on the “4M” strategy: measure, monitor, mainstream, and meet biodiversity goals.

Challenges and Regulatory Needs in Biodiversity Financing

Ms. Cornelia Neumann from Oliver Wyman pointed out that many elements of biodiversity financing currently lack clear business cases, which deters private investment. Adjusting the regulatory environment to recognize companies' impacts on nature and increasing the focus on reducing environmental pressures will help businesses integrate biodiversity considerations more effectively. Shifting these norms within the regulatory framework will enable smoother transitions for companies aiming to align with biodiversity goals.

The Role of Domestic Financial Institutions and Investor Trust

Mr. Michael Hillary from the Development Bank of South Africa stressed the importance of building investor trust to secure biodiversity financing. Ensuring investor returns and creating innovative trust mechanisms will help attract funding. Domestic and regional banks, especially development finance institutions (DFIs), play a critical bridging role in facilitating the flow of capital toward biodiversity projects.

OECD's Approach to Governance, Incentives, and Measurement

Ms. Kumi Kitamori from the OECD Environmental Directorate highlighted three immediate steps necessary to accelerate biodiversity financing. First, governance actions are needed to make effective use of public funds. Second, shifting economic incentives, such as focusing on Target 18 (reducing harmful subsidies) and promoting biodiversity-positive taxes, is vital. OECD's recent research shows that OECD nations currently generate around \$11 billion annually from such taxes. Third, improved measurement and transparency will allow for greater accountability. Some jurisdictions are moving to make voluntary biodiversity reporting mandatory, such as through the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD) and the Science-Based Targets Network (SBTN).

In 2022, the OECD produced a comprehensive overview of biodiversity finance flows, indicating that funds doubled from \$3.7 billion to \$15.4 billion, primarily from multilateral sources and private finance. Despite this progress, multilateral flows represent only 3 percent of the total, leaving significant room for development finance and nature-based solutions (NbS) to address biodiversity goals. Governments play a crucial role in fostering these initiatives.

Investment Screening and the Role of Biodiversity Credits

Mr. Bertrand Millot from CDPQ (Caisse de dépôt et placement du Québec) underscored that finance plays a pivotal role in biodiversity restoration by promoting organic practices and addressing industrial agriculture's impact on natural ecosystems. CDPQ is actively screening investments for environmental impact and collaborates on biodiversity initiatives with organizations like the Principles for Responsible Investment (PRI), Nature100, and FAIR (focused on animal welfare). Millot emphasized the need for a robust regulatory framework, governmental incentives, and the development of biodiversity credits to make measurable progress in biodiversity financing.

SESSION 4. Green Zone Event hosted by Global Environment Facility (GEF)

Target 18: Creating the Right Incentives for a Nature-Positive Future

Opening Plenary Session: Leadership and Financing for Biodiversity

Moderator Dr. Rosina Bierbaum, the Chair of the Science and Technology Advisory Panel of Global Environment Facility (GEF) led the session, featuring a diverse panel discussing key themes in biodiversity financing and policy reform.

IMF's Environmental Outcomes

Mr. Prasad Ananthakrishman from the IMF presented insights from a recent paper on nature and financial risks, revealing that \$1.7 trillion in global subsidies currently goes to harmful fossil fuels. Additionally, 38% of loans from the world's largest banks fund harmful sectors, which presents substantial risks. The IMF recommends that its 192 member countries adopt strategies focused on climate risk mitigation and adaptation. A sustainability trust has been created to provide long-term, low-interest loans to climate-vulnerable nations.

Government Policy and Environmental Action in Colombia

Mr. Carlos Correa, former Environment Minister of Colombia, addressed the political commitment and resource allocation needed for Colombia's climate actions. The country has protected 37% of its ocean area and 31% of its continental territory, yet still faces a financial gap. To address this, Colombia has strengthened its Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), introduced climate action laws in Congress, and formed a climate action cabinet.

Economic Reform and Harmful Subsidies

Ms. Eva Zabey from Business for Nature discussed the global economy's dependence on nature and the tendency for short-term economic gains to drive decision-making. She argued that reforming harmful subsidies could create jobs and enhance resilience, emphasizing the need for businesses to identify their reliance on these subsidies and support economic transitions.

Role of Civil Society in Biodiversity Policy Reform

Ms. Patricia Zurita from Conservation International noted a \$700 billion annual finance gap for biodiversity conservation, with \$500 billion in harmful subsidies that could be redirected. Civil society, she explained, is crucial in uniting stakeholders and providing data to clarify who benefits and who loses from subsidies. Conservation International works with international and national partners to support policy reform through initiatives like the Rights Coalition (RC), which engages key stakeholders.

Balancing Environmental and Economic Trade-Offs

Dr. Valerie Hickey from the World Bank spoke on the detrimental impacts of agricultural subsidies, particularly on deforestation and water pollution in Africa. She stressed the need for honest discussions and accurate data to facilitate decision-making and ensure the inclusion of low-income countries, indigenous peoples, small-scale farmers, and local NGOs in the process.

Achieving Biodiversity Target 18

Panelists emphasized the importance of policy coherence and financing for achieving Target 18, with a focus on public-private partnerships (PPPs), risk sharing, and capacity building. Involving local communities, subnational governments, and mayors is critical, as is celebrating creativity, youth engagement, technology, and success stories to sustain momentum.

Key Themes

The session underscored the importance of leadership, collaboration, and partnerships for effective climate action. Innovation, creativity, and accurate data are essential for successful policy implementation. Measuring co-benefits and engaging diverse stakeholders are key to comprehensive and inclusive climate strategies.

Parallel Session: Private Sector Leadership in Biodiversity

The session highlighted how the private sector can lead in biodiversity conservation and align with nature-positive strategies.

Private Sector Advocacy for Fossil Fuel Subsidy Reform

Ms. Callie Stinson from We Mean Business noted the increasing allocation of fossil fuel subsidies, now totaling \$1.5 trillion. Businesses are actively lobbying for subsidy reforms at international and regional levels.

Aligning Public and Private Financing

Ms. Stephania Avanzini from the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD) estimated that \$44 billion is needed to align public and private financing for biodiversity. She highlighted collaboration with farmers and agribusinesses as essential to transition away from harmful incentives.

Regenerative Agriculture and Corporate Strategy

Dr. Helen Crowley from Pollination promoted regenerative agriculture as a profitable and resilient approach. She encouraged framing biodiversity as an opportunity and incorporating externalities into corporate strategies.

Innovations in Agriculture and Partnerships

Ms. Natasha Sentos from the Private Sector Advisory emphasized the role of innovation in agriculture, such as drought-resistant seeds, crop rotation, and digital solutions. She stressed the need for partnerships to advance biological crop protection.

Technological Advancements in ASEAN Agriculture

Mr. Christoph Neumann from CropLife reported that ASEAN countries are increasingly using drones in agriculture, calling for science-based approaches to repurpose agricultural incentives.

Brazil's Supply Chain and Market Innovations

A Vice President from WBCSD described Brazil's focus on enhancing supply chains, promoting innovation, and reaching direct markets. He called for improved borrowing practices and the integration of nature-based metrics in financing.

Discussion Outcomes

Participants discussed the benefits of subsidy repurposing, noting that businesses gain from positive incentives and long-term sustainability while community-level governance fosters innovation and reduces reputational risk. Challenges discussed included limited land access, high innovation costs, lack of biodiversity data, and regulatory barriers. Key recommendations were to eliminate harmful subsidies, adopt landscape approaches, increase transparency, and offer preferential loans for sustainable practices.

Closing Plenary Session: Strategic Directions for Biodiversity Conservation

Moderator Dr. Rosina Bierbaum led a final panel exploring innovative solutions for financing biodiversity and addressing harmful subsidies.

Brazil's Biodiversity and Bioeconomy Leadership

Ms. Maria Neto from Instituto Climate Sociedade discussed Brazil's potential to support restoration efforts and reduce emissions through biodiversity conservation. Brazil's economy is deeply tied to natural resources, making government involvement essential. The country launched a bioeconomy plan and actively participates in G20 platforms to promote nature-based solutions. Policies are being developed to integrate incentives and biodiversity monitoring, with regenerative agriculture and insurance among key focuses.

Sweden's Efforts in Subsidy Policy Reform

Mr. Jakob Granit from the Swedish International Development Agency highlighted Sweden's approach to reforming subsidy policies, focusing on mobilizing private sector investments. Sweden works with the FAO and UN Global Compact to address fossil fuel subsidies and is developing business models and policy frameworks in cooperation with the EU to minimize subsidy-related risks.

Integrating Biodiversity into the Bioeconomy and Climate Pathways

Mr. Jose Manuel Salazar from UN ECLAC called for a transformative growth model that prioritizes sustainable bio-sectors. He underscored the need to shift production and consumption patterns and to regenerate ecosystems. Crop production's reliance on pollination highlights biodiversity's importance, while diversifying energy sources can mitigate drought-related disruptions. Investment in biodiversity must be scaled up, with a focus on building institutional capacity for transformative actions.

Pathways for Private Financing and Philanthropy

Mr. Cristian Samper from the Bezos Earth Fund described philanthropy's role in driving biodiversity conservation by providing rapid funding and supporting innovation. Positive incentives require accurate data, and platforms like the World Resources Institute's Global Forest Watch are expanding to monitor more ecosystems. Capacity building and providing de-risking guarantees for philanthropic investments are essential strategies, and AI is being explored for subsidy reform despite complex data requirements.

Key Takeaways

Mr. Jose Manuel Salazar emphasized the importance of data analytics, research, and subsidy mapping for effective reforms. Mr. Jakob Granit pointed to the role of political economy in financing biodiversity initiatives. Mr. Cristian Samper questioned whether current targets like Target 19 are sufficient, given the rising levels of harmful subsidies. Ms. Maria Neto concluded that tailored economic approaches and tools, including payments for ecosystem services (PES) and policy incentives, are needed to balance nature and human needs effectively.

Image source: Global Environment Facility

TECHNOLOGY AND BIODIVERSITY

SESSION 1. A Global Knowledge Support Service for Biodiversity (GKSSB)

UNEP-WCMC and COP16 Preparations

Ms. Natasha Ali from UNEP-WCMC is overseeing initiatives to enhance technical tools for biodiversity monitoring. In 2023, a co-design workshop was conducted to involve users in developing these tools, and further consultations with technical users are scheduled for 2025. A draft design will be presented at COP16 to allow stakeholders to provide feedback and ensure the tools meet user needs.

GKSSB and Kunming-Montreal Framework

The GKSSB website offers users a platform to filter biodiversity data according to Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF) targets. This tool is being introduced in two phases: the first focuses on monitoring and implementation using existing resources, while the second phase will incorporate an online reporting tool linked to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) to streamline data submission and analysis.

Link to GKSSB Website: <https://gkssb.chm-cbd.net/>

European Commission's Knowledge Center for Biodiversity

The European Commission's Knowledge Center for Biodiversity (KCBD) supports biodiversity tracking in the EU through tools like the EU Biodiversity Actions Tracker and the EI Biodiversity Dashboard. These tools facilitate reporting, enhance public awareness, and monitor the EU Biodiversity Strategy. Data is gathered from Eurostat, the Joint Research Center, the European Environment Agency, and EU-funded projects, which together feed into the Biodiversity Information Database (BID) for centralized information.

ASEAN Biodiversity Data and Technical and Scientific Cooperation Mechanism (TSCC) Platform

The ASEAN region has established the TSCC platform to host regional biodiversity workshops and continually update the ASEAN biodiversity data information platform. This knowledge management resource, accessible to ASEAN member states, was recently showcased at the ASEAN Pavilion in COP16 and serves as a key repository for regional biodiversity information.

CBD Secretariat's Global Coordination Entity

Mr. Ray Goh from the CBD Secretariat is developing a Global Coordination Entity tasked with managing a helpdesk for biodiversity data coordination. This helpdesk will provide technical support and advice to regional centers while gathering feedback from communities to improve biodiversity datasets, addressing some of the uncertainties inherent in managing biodiversity data.

UN Biodiversity Lab (UNBL)

According to Ms. Annie Virnig, the UN Biodiversity Lab (UNBL), managed by UNDP, is an open-source platform that offers high-quality spatial data layers and analytical tools to support biodiversity monitoring. The platform plays a crucial role in the Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) monitoring framework by providing access to spatial data and maps essential for national biodiversity reporting.

Link to UN Biodiversity Lab: www.unbiodiversitylab.org

FAO Biodiversity Knowledge Hub

The FAO Biodiversity Knowledge Hub adds further support, contributing valuable data and resources to the global biodiversity knowledge network. This platform complements other tools by broadening access to biodiversity information and enhancing knowledge sharing among stakeholders.

SESSION 2. Artificial Intelligence (AI) & Conservation

Panel Discussion on Conservation Technology: Key Insights and Future Directions

Moderator Ms. Stephanie O'Donnell from Wildlabs led a discussion centered on the intersection of technology and conservation.

Overview of Participants and Initiatives

Wildlabs, a collaborative network involving WWF, Conservation International, Wildlife Conservation Society, and Flora and Fauna International, is focused on advancing conservation technology. Mr. Paul Bunje of Conservation X Lab discussed his organization's work as a technology innovation lab aimed at preventing biodiversity loss and the sixth mass extinction. Conservation X Lab focuses on scaling technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI) and genetic tools, to combat biodiversity loss, supporting innovators across 80 countries. Mr. Jes Lefcourt from Allen Ai highlighted his organization's use of sensors and data aggregation tools to support conservation efforts, with a focus on collecting diverse data sources for ecosystem monitoring and management. Professor Tanya Berger-Wolf from Ohio State University outlined her work with machine learning and geo-vision, particularly through the development of AI models that analyze climate change impacts on biodiversity in data-scarce taxa, regions, and ecological regimes.

Future of Conservation Technology and Challenges

Mr. Bunje pointed out that conservation technology innovation has been slower than in other fields due to the complex nature of biodiversity. Understanding and addressing these intricacies is crucial for designing effective conservation solutions. Professor Berger-Wolf shared a vision of fully integrating technology and conservation, dissolving boundaries between tech and nature to foster innovation that directly benefits ecosystems. Mr. Lefcourt emphasized the importance of mission-driven data collection, particularly through remote sensing and satellites, suggesting that data must be aggregated and applied toward specific conservation goals rather than simply accumulated for its own sake. A representative from Wildlabs noted that data on wildlife management currently lacks usability and accessibility and that transforming this data into actionable formats is essential, as is engaging underrepresented communities in conservation technology conversations.

The Role of Partnerships in Conservation Technology

Mr. Lefcourt explained that data is often treated as a proprietary asset by organizations and governments, which limits its potential applications. This view of data needs to shift toward shared use, particularly as academic funding structures often emphasize data uniqueness over broader impact, which restricts data-sharing. Professor Berger-Wolf argued that data sharing in conservation requires a fundamental rethinking, particularly in emphasizing the tangible value of shared data in biodiversity efforts, given the lack of existing data governance frameworks for biodiversity. Mr. Bunje highlighted the need for strong incentives and frameworks that promote data sharing among corporations, governments, and local communities. Collaborative funding structures could create incentives to address these needs, especially in areas with data that directly influences conservation outcomes, such as weather patterns. A representative from Wildlabs emphasized that funding for partnerships and collaboration is crucial to maximizing the effectiveness of conservation technology.

The Role of Industry and Commercializing Conservation Technology

Mr. Bunje stressed the importance of commercializing conservation technology through entrepreneurial efforts, particularly in regions like Africa, to bridge funding gaps. Innovation in conservation technology is increasingly emerging from marginal economies, pushing the next wave of tech-based conservation solutions.

Balancing Technology and Conservation Goals

Professor Berger-Wolf emphasized that technological tools, such as affordable and simple AI applications, can empower broad participation in conservation. Designers, social scientists, and artists play vital roles in making technology accessible, with a focus on democratizing conservation efforts and ensuring that technology serves as an enabler rather than an end goal. A representative from Wildlabs added that while some countries have monitoring programs, effective conservation technology requires knowledge-sharing and relationship-building between nations.

Strategies for Achieving 30x30 Targets

Professor Berger-Wolf recommended several key strategies to achieve 30x30 targets, including enhancing algorithms and tools, improving data structures and infrastructure, engaging communities, building financing options, and focusing on capacity-building and education. The panel agreed that educating decision-makers is critical to closing knowledge gaps and strengthening AI-driven biodiversity conservation efforts.

Investment in Data Infrastructure and Capacity Building

Professor Berger-Wolf underscored the need for comprehensive data infrastructure investment and addressing biases in AI mapping. Investments in infrastructure and capacity building should prioritize tools that promote broad connectivity and engagement, ensuring that conservation technology's benefits are accessible across diverse populations and regions.

SCIENCE AND BIODIVERSITY

SESSION 1. Watering NBSAPs: Integrating Wetlands

Up to October 8th, 2024, 24 NBSAPs mentioned wetlands, inland waters, or freshwater. Some of them also mentioned specific types of wetlands such as peatlands and mangroves. The key findings are that 83% of the submitted NBSAPs include wetlands, inland waters or freshwater systems into their NBSAPs. They are mentioned among 18 out of 23 NBSAP targets, mostly in Target 1 (reduce biodiversity loss), 2 (restoration), and 3 (conservation). We also need to change the financial system right now to finance wetlands preservation.

(Notes are insufficient here due to data loss.)

SESSION 2. Plant Biodiversity

Diverse Ecosystems and Carbon Sequestration

Ms. Audrey Wagner from the Nature-based Solutions Initiative at the University of Oxford emphasized that diverse ecosystems are more effective in sequestering and storing carbon compared to monocultures, as noted in studies by Warner et al. (2023) and Schnabel et al. Additionally, Hutchison et al. (2018) found that more diverse planted forests exhibit greater resilience to climate extremes. Therefore, it is critical that restoration and reforestation efforts utilize a diverse range of native species. Monocultures should not be classified as Nature-based Solutions (NbS) since NbS must actively support and enhance both biodiversity and human well-being. Ms. Wagner advocated for policies at all levels to reflect this evidence and safeguard against misguided actions that may harm biodiversity in the pursuit of climate solutions.

Climate Conditions and Plant Diversity

Ms. Jiaze Li, a PhD candidate from Imperial College London, discussed the influence of climatic conditions on plant diversity. She explained that both spatial and temporal prevalence of climate conditions can promote high plant diversity. Variability in climate, both short-term and long-term, affects species richness by influencing the area and isolation of recent climates, as well as the movement of climate analogues. Ms. Li also suggested potential applications of climate analogues in biodiversity conservation.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Biodiversity Conservation

Professor Tanya Berger-Wolf from Ohio State University highlighted the urgent issue of biodiversity loss, stating that species are disappearing faster than they can be identified. She pointed out a significant data and resource gap in biodiversity studies, necessitating stronger connections to biodiversity data, akin to satellite monitoring for trees. Ecosystems are complex, and while we may understand certain components, our knowledge of entire systems is limited.

Professor Berger-Wolf explained that AI can play a key role by capturing numerous images of ecosystems, analyzing them to identify and count species, including individual animals. Currently, the accuracy of AI applications in biodiversity monitoring ranges from 83% to 92%, indicating a need for enhanced policy support to improve this accuracy further. Also, this work requires substantial resources. The funding gap for conservation efforts stands at approximately \$700 billion, and challenges such as a lack of coordination and policy further complicate the situation.

In response, recommendations from the Global Partnership on Artificial Intelligence (GPAI) emphasize the need to support biodiversity data openness and availability, prioritize outreach to local communities, and advocate for increased funding from governmental and multilateral sources. Establishing a global network of policy and practice AI tools, such as the ABC (AI and Biodiversity Change) Global Climate Center, is also essential.

SESSION 3. Coral Reef in the Latin America and the Caribbean

Importance of Community Engagement

In Grenada, community involvement plays a central role in coral reef management, especially as coastal areas face the increasing impact of natural disasters, such as hurricanes. Coastal communities often have firsthand knowledge that complements scientific research, which makes them valuable partners in conservation. Strengthening these communities is crucial, as they may hold insights and traditional knowledge that external experts lack. Given the pressures of coral bleaching and the importance of coral diversity, community-driven strategies, particularly in the restoration of species, are essential to successful reef management.

Bridging Scientific and Local Knowledge Gaps

To foster effective collaboration, it is vital to bridge the gaps between scientific understanding and local community perspectives. Reaching out to local stakeholders, especially those whose livelihoods depend on the reefs, can drive meaningful change. Engaging Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs) offers insights into sustainable practices that align with both environmental and cultural priorities. Building this bridge requires focusing on the people with the greatest influence and helping them see the direct impact of reef health on their own lives and work.

Enhancing Access to Data and Information Sharing

International Organizations often face fewer barriers in accessing data, and thus, they should prioritize making this information available to regional universities and academic institutions across Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC). Engaging academic institutions, students, and young researchers in Grenada and the wider region strengthens local knowledge and involvement. This approach also extends to government engagement, as international funding often flows through government channels. For conservation efforts to be effective, these funds should support academia and local youth, who often lack insight into government initiatives at the national level. Improved transparency across governmental, academic, and community sectors is essential for conservation success.

Connections Between Ecosystems: Mangroves and Coral Reefs

Scientific advancements show that coral reefs and mangroves are closely interconnected, each playing a crucial role in coastal ecosystem resilience. While mangrove conservation has seen significant breakthroughs, research on coral reefs is advancing, particularly in tracking reef health and resilience. Streamlined funding is needed to consolidate coral reef preservation efforts, rather than dispersing resources across multiple projects. The International Coral Reef Initiative (ICRI) and Caribbean Biodiversity Fund (CBF) are examples of collaborative platforms that could benefit from increased alignment in funding and goals. The Caribbean's regional reporting systems contrast with the Pacific's lack of similar mechanisms, underscoring governance and data-sharing barriers that impede collaborative efforts, especially when collecting benthic data from countries like Colombia.

Challenges in Coral Reef Preservation

Preserving coral reefs faces significant challenges, primarily in scaling community knowledge and experiences to support large-scale projects. Regional collaboration across Caribbean nations is needed, but logistical and educational barriers exist, particularly in areas with extensive archipelagos, such as the Bahamas. Education is critical in the Bahamas, where locals need training in coral disease identification and reef surveys. Organizations like the Bahamas Reef Foundation, Friends of the Environment, and the Bahamas Environmental Trust provide valuable contributions to local conservation efforts. Combining formal scientific data with informal, community-sourced knowledge will strengthen these initiatives, reinforcing a community-based approach to coral reef conservation.

The Role of OECMs in Conservation

Other Effective Area-Based Conservation Measures (OECMs) present an opportunity to involve communities directly in science-based conservation. OECMs promote a participatory model that empowers local populations to lead on-the-ground efforts, making conservation both scientifically rigorous and culturally relevant.

SESSION 4. RRREEF – Artificial reef made out of Terra-cotta

The non-profit coral reef conservation organization named 'Rrreef' introduced their artificial reefs made out of terra-cotta and showed the process on building the structures under the sea of Philippines and the Latin America and Caribbean regions, with some pictures and recorded videos on marine ecosystems gathering and resting at the artificial reefs. The team used terra-cottas as materials because of its porosity, which makes the aquatic animals easier to forage and effectively hide from the predators. Also, they mentioned that a lot of carbons are emitted when making a traditional cement, while renewable energy can be used to make a terra-cotta. Lastly, terra-cotta does not typically require sands as materials, which is relatively a limited resource on the Earth.

Above is the image of the miniature figures of the artificial terra-cotta reefs.

INDIGENOUS PEOPLE AND BIODIVERSITY

SESSION 1. Press conference on Nature & Indigenous People

An Indigenous spokesperson from Ecuador: Amazon Protection and the Marketization of Nature

In 2019, an Ecuadorian judge from Colombia ruled in favor of protecting the Amazon for future generations, declaring that nature's value should not be reduced to mere market transactions. This decision underscored a critique of traditional markets, which often prioritize profit over genuine environmental care. When nature is commodified, true stewardship is often lost.

Indigenous Perspective from Oklahoma, United States of America: Human Inseparability from Nature

An Indigenous voice from Oklahoma emphasized that humans are inseparable from nature. Our dependency on clean air, water, and food underscores this connection. The destructive practices of extractive industries—like mining and drilling—harm natural ecosystems, polluting rivers and damaging the very elements we rely on. Carbon sequestration and offset schemes, often tied to biodiversity credits, are seen as false solutions, enabling companies to continue polluting under the guise of “green” credits.

A Call for Systemic Change

The need is clear: we must transition away from fossil fuels and reimagine capitalism. The focus should shift from nature as a commodity to nature as a holistic, protected system. This calls for a fundamental change in government tracking and policies, moving away from biodiversity credits and towards sustainable, system-wide norms for environmental protection.

SESSION 2. Building the Future of Environmental Decision-making

Equitable Access to Nature's Benefits for Local Communities

Ensuring equitable access to the benefits of nature is essential for supporting local communities and ending a legacy of nature ignorance. By prioritizing community-based natural resource management, conservation efforts can be more effective and sustainable. This approach empowers communities to participate in and benefit from the protection of their local environments.

Benefit Sharing and Conservation Mechanisms

To foster sustainable conservation, benefit-sharing instruments and mechanisms are critical. These tools allow communities to gain tangible rewards from conservation activities, strengthening their commitment to preserving nature. Both market-based and non-market-based approaches are important in achieving this goal, as they provide flexible frameworks for different contexts and needs. However, barriers remain, particularly for small and rural communities, where limited access to resources and knowledge can hinder participation.

Challenges with Funding and Capacity Building

Many rural and small communities are dependent on external funding, creating a vulnerability in conservation efforts. This reliance can be destabilizing, especially if funding sources are inconsistent. For conservation projects to be impactful, local communities must have the capacity to manage these resources independently, without constant dependence on external support. Capacity-building efforts are, therefore, essential for long-term sustainability.

Public Policy Instruments and Governance

Public policy instruments play a central role in promoting biodiversity and ecosystem services. International frameworks and governance models provide guidance and support to align local conservation efforts with global standards. Through effective governance, conservation practices can be standardized, monitored, and refined to achieve greater consistency and accountability.

CASE STUDY ON BIODIVERSITY

SESSION 1. Regional Flyway Initiative

Innovative Financial Mechanisms for Biodiversity

Mr. Martin Harper from the BirdLife International emphasized the urgent need for innovative financial mechanisms and the active involvement of civil society in addressing biodiversity challenges. He highlighted that collaboration is essential to mobilize resources effectively.

Regional Flyway Initiative and Investment in Wetland Protection

Mr. Duncan Lang from the Asian Development Bank (ADB) discussed the Regional Flyway Initiative (RFI), which aims to mobilize \$3 billion in investments for wetland protection and management to achieve a flyway-level impact. This initiative is aligned with various organizations, including the East Asian-Australasian Flyway Partnership (EAAFP), the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (UNCBD), the Ramsar Convention, and UNESCO. The RFI consists of two phases: Phase 1, from 2021 to 2024, focuses on project development, while Phase 2, from 2024 onward, will emphasize implementation with a goal to improve 50 wetlands. This effort also contributes to ADB's \$100 billion climate resilience project, with a site selection process identifying 147 priority wetland sites across the East Asian-Australasian Flyway. Funding for this initiative includes \$100,000 from USAID, \$100,000 from the Global Environment Facility (GEF), and support from the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation.

Mobilizing Public and Blended Funding

Mr. Marshall Johnson from the Audubon discussed the need to harness and catalyze the American Flyways Initiative, stressing the importance of focusing on specific goals to effectively enhance biodiversity. He pointed out the alarming statistic that since 1970, there has been a loss of 3 billion birds in the Western Hemisphere, highlighting the urgency of mobilizing more public and blended funding to address this crisis.

Integrating Biodiversity into Activities

Ms. Marie-Cécile Thirion from the French Development Agency (AFD) shared that AFD is seeking financing to support ADB in the Regional Flyway Initiative. She noted that managing migrating birds is generally easier than managing wetlands but emphasized the need to integrate biodiversity considerations into all activities and eliminate those that harm it.

Biodiversity and Risk Management

Ms. Ruth Tiffer-Sotomayor, a Senior Biodiversity Specialist at the World Bank, posed a question about the potential of flyways to enhance biodiversity, noting the need for a nature-positive approach. She mentioned that the World Bank requires specific standards to reduce impacts on biodiversity, including migratory species. In collaboration with the African Development Bank (AfDB), the World Bank aims to ramp up Nature-based Solutions (NbS) across various sectors, including agriculture and water, to attract positive investments that will also benefit local communities.

Wetlands Protection and Ecosystem-Based Approaches

Mr. Wataru Suzuki from the Ministry of the Environment in Japan discussed the critical role of wetlands for bird survival. He questioned the need to preserve wetlands rather than reclaim them, highlighting that access to Nature-based Solutions can be limited in developed countries. He mentioned Japan's increased investment in ecosystem-based approaches following the massive tsunami happened in 2011, reflecting a commitment to biodiversity.

Closing Remarks from Ramsar Secretariat

Mr. Jerker Tamelander from the Ramsar Secretariat provided closing remarks, reinforcing the importance of collaborative efforts and innovative financing in the protection of wetlands and migratory birds.

Image source: East Asian-Australasian Flyway Partnership Secretariat

To learn more about the Regional Flyway Initiative, please visit the website:
<https://eaaflwyway.net/regional-flyway-initiative/>

APPENDICES

Appendix 1.

23 Targets of Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework

Target	Description
1	Plan and Manage all Areas To Reduce Biodiversity Loss
2	Restore 30% of all Degraded Ecosystems
3	Conserve 30% of Land, Waters and Seas
4	Halt Species Extinction, Protect Genetic Diversity, and Manage Human-Wildlife Conflicts
5	Ensure Sustainable, Safe and Legal Harvesting and Trade of Wild Species
6	Reduce the Introduction of Invasive Alien Species by 50% and Minimize Their Impact
7	Reduce Pollution to Levels That Are Not Harmful to Biodiversity
8	Minimize the Impacts of Climate Change on Biodiversity and Build Resilience
9	Manage Wild Species Sustainably To Benefit People
10	Enhance Biodiversity and Sustainability in Agriculture, Aquaculture, Fisheries, and Forestry
11	Restore, Maintain and Enhance Nature's Contributions to People

Target	Description
12	Enhance Green Spaces and Urban Planning for Human Well-Being and Biodiversity
13	Increase the Sharing of Benefits From Genetic Resources, Digital Sequence Information and Traditional Knowledge
14	Integrate Biodiversity in Decision-Making at Every Level
15	Businesses Assess, Disclose and Reduce Biodiversity-Related Risks and Negative Impacts
16	Enable Sustainable Consumption Choices To Reduce Waste and Overconsumption
17	Strengthen Biosafety and Distribute the Benefits of Biotechnology
18	Reduce Harmful Incentives by at Least \$500 Billion per Year, and Scale Up Positive Incentives for Biodiversity
19	Mobilize \$200 Billion per Year for Biodiversity From all Sources, Including \$30 Billion Through International Finance
20	Strengthen Capacity-Building, Technology Transfer, and Scientific and Technical Cooperation for Biodiversity
21	Ensure That Knowledge Is Available and Accessible To Guide Biodiversity Action
22	Ensure Participation in Decision-Making and Access to Justice and Information Related to Biodiversity for all
23	Ensure Gender Equality and a Gender-Responsive Approach for Biodiversity Action

Appendix 2.

17 Megadiverse Countries

Data source: Conservation International, Image source: Wikipedia

- Australia
- Brazil
- China
- Colombia
- Democratic Republic of Congo
- Ecuador
- India
- Indonesia
- Madagascar
- Malaysia
- Mexico
- Papua New Guinea
- Peru
- Philippines
- South Africa
- United States of America
- Venezuela

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